

PERFORATED COMPOSITE PLATES
EFFECTS OF THE CURVATURE ON THREE DIMENSIONAL
STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS AROUND HOLES
COMPARISON BETWEEN TWO DIFFERENT METHODS

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ABSTRACT

The edge effects around the hole in a composite laminate perforated plate are commonly admitted to be delamination initiators.

For a design purpose to counteract this phenomenon, reliable computation of the local 3D stress field is needed.

In this study, two specific and original methods are compared, the first relying on a true boundary layer formulation with a semi-discrete numerical solution, and the second on a damage mechanics non linear F.E.M. approach. Though the second has far greater capability for crack initiation and delamination studies, it appeared important to make first comparisons in pure elasticity theory.

Four values of radius to thickness ratios for an unloaded hole are considered (100, 10, 1, 1/3) for an eight layer quasi-isotropic T300/914 CFRP composite plate. It is shown that for large hole diameters the two methods are in fairly good agreement whereas, for smaller holes, the boundary layer method, which relies on an asymptotic formulation, can result in serious errors. One counterpart is that the second method is currently limited to circular hole shapes, whilst the first can handle any shape, provided that the local curvature is not too high.

KEYWORDS: Plates; Holes; Delamination; Edge/Effects; Interlaminar/Stresses.

1. INTRODUCTION

Assessment of the delamination tendency in composite laminated structures is of particular importance in industrial design.

This phenomenon is often design driver, in fact, in every location where stress and strain gradients are high: in these areas, even for thin plates or shells, the stress field is three-dimensional in nature.

Thereby the laminates are loaded in a direction where, due to their lack of normal reinforcement, their strength is very weak.

The present study deals especially with the perforated plate problem, currently encountered in aircraft and spacecraft structures.

Up to now, this problem has given rise to much research, dedicated to the two main concerns: delamination initiation prediction and analysis of an existing delaminated area.

Most studies relevant to the second point involve extensions of Fracture Mechanics, a theory which is widely used for metallic materials.

In this paper, we have focused on delamination initiation. Industrial approaches to this problem today involve empirical criteria such as "point-stress" or "average stress". These criteria require many tests, and the parameters have to be fitted for each stacking sequence. Although they allow a pragmatic investigation of failure around holes, they cannot really be considered as predictive tools.

The French Space Agency is supporting important work in national industry and research laboratories whose aim is to develop more phenomenological and predictive approaches to delamination. In fact, delamination is a complex phenomenon resulting from various interacting intra and inter-laminar damages, which begin mostly initiates near the edges where, as we mentioned, the stress field is three-dimensional. Thorough knowledge and understanding of delamination thus need a reliable calculation of these local stresses.

A first range of methods investigated hereafter is based upon the analysis of the peeling and shearing inter-laminar stresses around the hole in pure elasticity. These methods may be used to compare the delamination tendency of various stacking sequences.

Such approach, proposed by D. ENGRAND [1] has been programmed in a computer software CLEOPS. This software [2], today used for engineering design purposes in aerospace industry, relies on a quasi-analytical formulation, and allows a fast, accurate and cost-effective computation of these stresses. In the future, this approach is hoped to lead to a simplified predictive criterion for delamination resistance from a quantitative analysis of the stress profiles near the edge.

Another, more complete approach, but still in the area of research, takes into account, through the Damage Mechanics of Composite Materials proposed by P. LADEVEZE [3], the various degradation processes interacting in the laminate. This will allow us to predict delamination initiation and propagation far more precisely, and to include these two aspects in a single model.

DSDM software [4], relying on this formulation, has been developed for the analysis of this phenomenon around circular holes in laminated plates. Devoted to a 3D non linear calculation, it may of course be used for stresses computation in pure elasticity.

It is within this framework of elasticity theory that the two computational tools have been compared. The purposes of the study were:

- validation of the elastic stresses computation for the research software DSDM,

- quantitative evaluation of the applicability limits of CLEOPS software, whose formulation (asymptotic method) requires the hypothesis of small ratio h/R (h = laminate thickness ; R = hole radius).

2. THE PERFORATED PLATE PROBLEM

The comparison between the two methods has been performed on the reference case of an infinite eight layers $[0, 45, -45, 90]_S$ T300/914 CFRP laminate plate with hole. The plate is loaded with an averaged unit tensile stress at infinity parallel to upper ply fibre direction (see figure 1).

FIGURE 1. The perforated plate problem

Elastic properties of the elementary ply:

$E_1 = 148 \text{ GPa}$

$E_2 = E_3 = 11,5 \text{ GPa}$

$G_{12} = G_{13} = G_{23} = 5,8 \text{ GPa}$

$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = \nu_{23} = 0,33$

(1 refers to fibre direction, 2 in-plane transverse direction, 3 normal direction).

The three-dimensional problem to solve is:

Find (σ, \bar{u}) satisfying

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \text{div}(\sigma) = \bar{0} & \text{in } \Omega \\ \sigma = A \cdot \varepsilon(\bar{u}) & \text{in } \Omega \\ \sigma \cdot \bar{n} = \bar{0} & \text{on } \Gamma = \delta\Omega - (\Gamma_- \cup \Gamma_+) \\ \sigma \cdot \bar{n} = \pm \bar{F} & \text{on } \Gamma_{\pm} \\ \sigma \cdot \bar{n} \text{ and } \bar{u} & \text{continuous on the interfaces} \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

Four values of radius to thickness ratios have been considered:

$R/h = 100 ; R/h = 10 ; R/h = 1 ; R/h = 1/3$

The greatest value allows a comparison of the two calculations in a case where the asymptotic method applicability is well stated. The other values permit both an investigation of the limits of this method, and a parametric study of the influence of the hole radius on the 3D stress field. This

can be achieved with the second method, which does not enclose any theoretical limitation on R/h magnitude in its formulation.

3. NUMERICAL METHODS

3.1 CLEOPS software The principle of the method, pioneered by Friedrichs and Dressler [5], and by Tang for composite laminated plates [6] consists in correcting the plane stress field derived from a classical plate theory (Kirchoff-Love in our case) in the area around the hole (edge area), where the stresses are, in fact, three-dimensional. This correction is achieved by superimposing on the plane stress field σ^{CP} a 3D stress field F so that the resulting tensor $(\sigma^{CP} + F)$ exactly verifies all the equations of the complete three-dimensional problem (1). When considering σ^{CP} as a given plane tensor, the corrector F then can be entirely derived from these equations [2, 7].

Assuming the ratio R/h to be much larger than one, we can develop F in power series of h , and solve the problem (1) keeping only F_0 , the first term of this asymptotic development.

It can be shown that, for this new problem, the orthoradial stress $\sigma_{\theta\theta}^{CP}$ in polar coordinates operates in the calculation as a parameter and that, for a given Θ , the initial 3D problem has only to be solved in the semi-infinite Θ -strip, which is a 2D domain usually called boundary layer domain (see figure 2) [8,9].

FIGURE 2. Boundary layer domain

The reduced coordinates in the strip are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \xi &= \frac{r-R}{h} & \xi &\in [0; +\infty[\\ \eta &= \frac{z}{h/2} & \eta &\in [-1; +1] \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, the problem is solved in the boundary layer domain $(\eta, \xi)_0$ using two stress functions ϕ and ψ such as:

$$F_{\theta r}^0 = \psi_{,\eta} \quad F_{\theta z}^0 = -\psi_{,\xi} \quad F_{rr}^0 = \phi_{,\eta\eta} \quad F_{rz}^0 = -\phi_{,\eta\xi} \quad F_{zz}^0 = \phi_{,\xi\xi}$$

For each radial strip corresponding to a value of Θ , the solution is obtained with a variational formulation in η of the local equations, leading to mono-dimensional finite elements in the thickness direction and a spectral decomposition of the stress functions in the depth (ξ direction).

Finally, the superimposition of σ^{CP} and F_0 give a good approximation of the local 3D stress field.

3.2 DSDM software A main characteristic of the Damage Mechanics models developed at LMT de l'ENS de Cachan for laminates, is a two elementary constituents representation: the single layer and the interface. These two constituents are damageable [10].

From a pure elastic analysis point of view, with respect to classical approaches, the interface behaviour is described by the constitutive law:

$$\sigma_n = [k] [U]$$

where $[U]$ denotes the displacements discontinuities between two adjacent layers, and $[k]$ is a stiffness matrix characteristic of the interface.

DSDM software, acting as a post-processor of a 2D plane-stress calculation, is devoted to the analysis of delamination around an initially circular hole.

The analysis is restricted within the vicinity of the edges in the domain Ω , where the three-dimensional effects are significant (see figure 3).

FIGURE 3. Strategy of the analysis with DSDM software

From a "shell" computation, a 3D displacement field for the $\delta_1\Omega$ area is constructed under the plane stress assumption. These displacements U_d become some of the prescribed displacements for the edge effect computation.

In order to solve at a reasonable computation cost, the non-linear three-dimensional evolution problem in Ω (which is the general purpose of the software), a semi-analytical method, hereafter briefly described, is used.

Semi-analytical method

The three-dimensional problems are reduced to two-dimensional ones in a finite strip by using (i) a conjugate gradient method and (ii) the F.F.T. An axially symmetric conditioned operator is used to solve non axially symmetric problems (because of the elastic constitutive law). The conjugate gradient method has become classical in its use.

The choice of the conditioner, and how it is used to compute a 3D displacement field is described here. Let us denote the conditioner by K_0 . The problem is solved iteratively by means of a series of intermediate problems :

$$K_0 X = F^{(i)} \quad \text{where } K_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} K_e d\theta \quad (K_e: \text{elasticity operator}) \quad (2)$$

The date $F^{(i)}$ of each problem is developed in Fourier series by means of the F.F.T. Then according to the axial symmetry of the problem (2), each component of the displacement is computed by means of a two-dimensional elastic problem (in a finite strip). This is which are solved by a Finite Element analysis. The 3D displacement field is then computed by F.F.T.⁻¹.

4. STRESS ANALYSIS

4.1 Plane stress calculation The starting point for the two methods is a "shell" computation of the plane stresses. This was performed with the NASTRAN Finite Element Code. Figure 4 shows, as expected in this case of a quasi-isotropic laminate, the main results concerning averaged orthoradial stress $\sigma_{\Theta\Theta}$ on the edge around the hole:

$$\sigma_{\Theta\Theta}(r = R, \Theta = 90^\circ) = 3 \sigma \quad \sigma_{\Theta\Theta}(r = R, \Theta = 0^\circ) = -1 \sigma$$

FIGURE 4. Shell computation of averaged plane stress (APS) around the hole and corresponding plane stress in the 0° layer (PS)

4.2 Comparison of the three-dimensional calculations

From the four computational cases investigated (corresponding to the various ratios R/h), a great amount of stress results has been derived [11] concerning:

- the corrected plane stresses $\sigma_{\Theta\Theta}$, $\sigma_{\Gamma\Gamma}$, $\sigma_{\Gamma\Theta}$, around the hole,
- the stress distribution patterns for σ_{ZZ} , $\sigma_{\Theta Z}$, $\sigma_{\Gamma Z}$ in the 0°, 45°, 90° strips of the laminate,
- the distribution around the hole of σ_{ZZ} , $\sigma_{\Theta Z}$, $\sigma_{\Gamma Z}$ in the middle of each layer,
- the stress distribution σ_{ZZ} , $\sigma_{\Theta Z}$, $\sigma_{\Gamma Z}$ along the different interfaces for the 0°, 45°, 90° strips.

For clarity and concision, only a few significant results are presented hereafter.

4.2.1 Orthoradial plane stress field correction

The edge effects not only concern σ_{ZZ} , $\sigma_{\Theta Z}$, $\sigma_{\Gamma Z}$, mainly responsible for delamination, but also affect the plane stresses around the hole. In some cases, these modifications may appear far from negligible.

Figure 5 illustrates this phenomenon for $\sigma_{\Theta\Theta}$ values on the hole edge in the middle of the 0° layer.

We can observe, when comparing with figure 4, that for small radius holes, the stress magnification is over 20 %.

FIGURE 5. $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$ stress on the edge around the hole in the middle of the 0° layer

Moreover, CLEOPS and DSDM ($r/h = 100$) calculations superimpose perfectly.

4.2.2 Peeling stress σ_{zz} σ_{zz} is plotted on figure 6 on the edge in the middle of the 90° layer, where max values are reached.

Distribution shapes are similar for great hole radii ($R/h > 10$) whereas, for small radii, the stress profiles are very disturbed and smaller in magnitude.

FIGURE 6. Peeling stress σ_{zz} around the hole in the middle of the 90° layer

Though the stress profiles concur well, some differences on the peak values appear between CLEOPS and DSDM ($R/h = 100$). This can be explained first by the fact that the stiffnesses of the interface elements in the DSDM calculations have been assumed a priori, without any further updating for an improved correlation.

Moreover, the stresses are calculated with CLEOPS exactly on the edge, whereas they are computed at gauss points with DSDM. Owing to the rapid decrease of σ_{ZZ} in depth, illustrated in figure 7 for the $90^\circ/90^\circ$ interface, the first method may lead to higher values on the edge.

FIGURE 7. σ_{zz} distribution along the interface $90^\circ/90^\circ$ in the strip $\Theta = 90^\circ$

4.2.3 Shearing stress $\sigma_{\Theta Z}$ The highest values for this stress are reached around the hole in the $\pm 45^\circ$ layers and on the interface between them. Figure 8 shows $\sigma_{\Theta Z}$ in the middle of the 45° layer on the edge.

Peak values appear for $\Theta \simeq 70^\circ$ for great hole radii and the stress profiles are still disturbed for smaller radii. Both methods are in good agreement.

FIGURE 8. Shearing stress σ_{OZ} around the hole in the middle of the 45° layer

Stress distributions along the interface $+45^\circ/-45^\circ$ in the $\Theta = 90^\circ$ strip also compare well (see figure 8) for the greatest hole radius ($R/h = 100$). Despite occurrence of a mathematical singularity for σ_{OZ} at the interface, located very close to of the edge [12], the stress intensity in the remote area is similarly accounted for by the two computations.

FIGURE 9. σ_{OZ} distribution along the interface $+45^\circ/-45^\circ$ in the strip $\Theta = 90^\circ$

4.2.4 Shearing stress σ_{TZ} This stress is equal to zero on the edge around the hole. This boundary condition is well related by the two methods (for CLEOPS, it is contained in the formulation). In any case, although its magnitude is, most of the time, lesser than for σ_{OZ} , σ_{TZ} reaches peak values on the interfaces at a distance from the edge varying between $0,1h$ and $0,5h$. Figure 9 illustrates this typical distribution for σ_{TZ} along the $+45^\circ/-45^\circ$ interface in the $\Theta = 90^\circ$ strip.

FIGURE 10. σ_{TZ} distribution along the interface $+45^\circ/-45^\circ$ in the strip $\Theta = 90^\circ$

5. CONCLUSION

This first study concerning two different methods for computing interlaminar stresses around a hole in a laminate has given satisfactory results. Further validation should be performed for other loading cases: bending moment, loaded hole.

The present study has proved that the hole radius has a great influence on interlaminar stress distributions and magnitudes around the hole and along the interfaces. Moreover, it appears that the prevailing delamination modes (due to peeling or shearing stresses) depend on the interface and on the strip considered, and it is hard to predict simply which one will initiate first.

A multicriteria approach based upon stress distribution along the interfaces, and not only upon max stress values, which are not significant in the presence of mathematical singularities, seems to be the way to investigate in the scope of a simplified approach for engineering design purpose. This has already been initiated by Kim and Al. in the case of a straight free edge in composite laminates [13, 14].

For the hole problem, it becomes most complicated due to the various parameters involved (radius to thickness ratio, stacking sequence evolving with Θ), and a systematic investigation is necessary. This can be achieved efficiently with CLEOPS software in the cases of great hole radii ($R/h > 10$).

Finally, we have to emphasize that a more complete approach of delamination based upon Damage Mechanics is very promising in the future, through the use of performant computational tools like DSDM.

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